

Metabolomic Profiles of Nonobese and Obese Women With Gestational Diabetes

Sormunen-Harju et al.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Supplementary Figure 1. Flowchart of the study

Supplementary Figure 2. Mean differences in 66 metabolic measures of nonobese women with GDM (NOGDM) (blue), obese women with GDM (OGDM) (red), and obese women with no GDM (O) (yellow) from nonobese controls with no GDM. Dots refer to the mean differences between the controls and the three study groups across early, mid-, and late pregnancy measurement points. Error bars refer to 99.8% CIs. Associations adjusted for cohort, gestational week at the time of blood sampling, maternal age, parity, education, and smoking and alcohol use during pregnancy.

Supplementary Figure 3. Mean differences in 66 metabolic measures of nonobese women with GDM (NOGDM) (blue), obese women with GDM (OGDM) (red) and obese women with no GDM (O) (yellow) from nonobese controls with no GDM. Dots refer to the mean differences between the controls and the three study at the early pregnancy measurement point. Error bars refer to 99.8% CIs. Associations adjusted for cohort, gestational week at blood sampling, maternal age, parity, education, and smoking, and alcohol use during pregnancy.

Supplementary Figure 4. Mean differences in change (estimates representing slopes) in 66 metabolic measures during pregnancy between nonobese women with GDM (NOGDM) (blue), obese women with GDM (OGDM) (red), and obese women with no GDM (O) (yellow), and the controls. Dots refer to the mean difference in change per one pregnancy week in these metabolic measures in SD units. Error bars refer to 99.8% CIs. Associations adjusted for cohort, maternal age, parity, education, and smoking and alcohol use during pregnancy. If the estimate representing the slope of change is negative, the metabolic measure increased less or decreased more, and if the estimate is positive, the metabolic measure increased more or decreased less during pregnancy in women with the condition than in the controls. The left panel shows the results for all women (n=755), and the right panel for women who provided data on metabolic measures at all three timepoints during pregnancy (n=535).

Supplementary Figure 5. Trajectories of the metabolic measures in which differences in change during pregnancy between obese women with GDM (OGDM) and the controls were more pronounced than differences between nonobese women with GDM (NOGDM) or obese women with no GDM (O) and controls (panel A); and trajectories of the metabolic measures in which differences in change during pregnancy between obese women with GDM (OGDM) or obese women with no GDM (O) and controls were more pronounced than differences between nonobese women with GDM (NOGDM) and controls (panel B).

Supplementary Table 1. Number and percentage of missingness per metabolic measure in the combined PREDO-RADIEL cohort.

Supplementary Table 2. Numeric values of mean differences and 99.8% CIs in the metabolic measures during pregnancy in which nonobese women with GDM (NOGDM), obese women with GDM (OGDM), and obese women with no GDM (O) differed similarly from the controls (Panel A); in which differences of obese women with GDM (OGDM) from controls were more pronounced than were the differences of NOGDM or O from controls (Panel B); and in which differences of OGDM or O from controls were more pronounced than differences of NOGDM from controls (Panel C). Numeric values seen in the left panels represent differences in the combined PREDO-RADIEL cohort, and in the right panels in the independent ITU replication cohort. Associations adjusted for cohort (PREDO-RADIEL), gestational week at blood sampling, maternal age, parity, education, and smoking and alcohol use during pregnancy.

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Supplementary Figure 2. (CONTINUED) Mean differences in 66 metabolic measures of nonobese women with GDM (NOGDM) (blue), obese women with GDM (OGDM) (red), and obese women with no GDM (O) (yellow) from nonobese controls-with no GDM. Dots refer to the mean differences between the controls and the three study groups across early, mid-, and late pregnancy measurement points. Error bars refer to 99.8% CIs. Associations adjusted for cohort, gestational week at blood sampling, maternal age, parity, education, and smoking and alcohol use during pregnancy.

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Lipoprotein subclasses

- Extremely large VLDL
- Very large VLDL
- Large VLDL
- Medium VLDL
- Small VLDL
- Very small VLDL
- IDL
- Large LDL
- Medium LDL
- Small LDL
- Very large HDL
- Large HDL
- Medium HDL
- Small HDL

Lipoprotein particle size

- Mean diameter for VLDL particles
- Mean diameter for LDL particles
- Mean diameter for HDL particles

Cholesterol

- Total cholesterol
- Total cholesterol in VLDL
- Total cholesterol in LDL
- Total cholesterol in HDL
- Remnant cholesterol
- Esterified cholesterol
- Free cholesterol

Glycerides and phospholipids

- Total triglycerides
- Triglycerides in VLDL
- Triglycerides in LDL
- Triglycerides in HDL
- Total phosphoglycerides
- Phosphatidylcholine and other cholines
- Total cholines
- Sphingomyelin

Apolipoproteins

- Apolipoprotein A-I
- Apolipoprotein B
- Ratio of apolipoprotein B to apolipoprotein A-I

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Fatty acids

- Docosahexaenoic acid
- Linoleic acid
- Omega-3 fatty acids
- Omega-6 fatty acids
- Polyunsaturated fatty acids
- Monounsaturated fatty acids
- Saturated fatty acids

Fatty acids ratios

- Docosahexaenoic acid to total fatty acids
- Linoleic acid to total fatty acids
- Omega-3 fatty acids to total fatty acids
- Omega-6 fatty acids to total fatty acids
- Polyunsaturated fatty acids to total fatty acids
- Monounsaturated fatty acids to total fatty acids
- Saturated fatty acids to total fatty acids

Glycolysis related metabolites

- Glucose
- Lactate
- Citrate

Amino acids

- Alanine
- Glutamine
- Histidine

Branched-chain amino acids

- Isoleucine
- Leucine
- Valine

Aromatic amino acids

- Phenylalanine
- Tyrosine

Ketone bodies

- Acetate
- Acetoacetate
- 3-hydroxybutyrate

Fluid balance

- Creatinine
- Albumin

Inflammation

- Glycoprotein acetyls

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Supplementary Table 1. Number and percentage of missingness per metabolic measure in the combined PREDO-RADIEL cohort.

Metabolic measure	Missing values at the first sampling point		Missing values at the second sampling point		Missing values at the third sampling point		Metabolic measure available at only one time point		Metabolic measure available at two time points		Metabolic measure available at all three time points	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Extremely large VLDL	117	15,5	72	9,5	77	10,2	48	6,4	170	22,5	537	71,1
Very large VLDL	119	15,8	72	9,5	77	10,2	48	6,4	172	22,8	535	70,9
Large VLDL	118	15,6	72	9,5	77	10,2	48	6,4	171	22,7	536	71,0
Medium VLDL	117	15,5	72	9,5	77	10,2	48	6,4	170	22,5	537	71,1
Small VLDL	117	15,5	72	9,5	77	10,2	48	6,4	170	22,5	537	71,1
Very small VLDL	117	15,5	72	9,5	77	10,2	48	6,4	170	22,5	537	71,1
IDL	117	15,5	72	9,5	77	10,2	48	6,4	170	22,5	537	71,1
Large LDL	117	15,5	72	9,5	77	10,2	48	6,4	170	22,5	537	71,1
Medium LDL	117	15,5	72	9,5	77	10,2	48	6,4	170	22,5	537	71,1
Small LDL	117	15,5	72	9,5	77	10,2	48	6,4	170	22,5	537	71,1
Very large HDL	117	15,5	72	9,5	77	10,2	48	6,4	170	22,5	537	71,1
Large HDL	118	15,6	73	9,7	77	10,2	48	6,4	170	22,5	537	71,1
Medium HDL	117	15,5	72	9,5	79	10,5	48	6,4	171	22,7	536	71,0
Small HDL	117	15,5	72	9,5	77	10,2	48	6,4	170	22,5	537	71,1
Mean diameter of VLDL particles	117	15,5	72	9,5	77	10,2	48	6,4	170	22,5	537	71,1
Mean diameter of LDL particles	117	15,5	74	9,8	78	10,3	49	6,5	171	22,7	535	70,9
Mean diameter of HDL particles	117	15,5	72	9,5	77	10,2	48	6,4	170	22,5	537	71,1
Total cholesterol	117	15,5	72	9,5	77	10,2	48	6,4	170	22,5	537	71,1

Total cholesterol in VLDL	117	15,5	72	9,5	77	10,2	48	6,4	170	22,5	537	71,1
Total cholesterol in LDL	117	15,5	72	9,5	77	10,2	48	6,4	170	22,5	537	71,1
Total cholesterol in HDL	117	15,5	72	9,5	77	10,2	48	6,4	170	22,5	537	71,1
Remnant cholesterol	117	15,5	72	9,5	77	10,2	48	6,4	170	22,5	537	71,1
Esterified cholesterol	117	15,5	72	9,5	77	10,2	48	6,4	170	22,5	537	71,1
Free cholesterol	117	15,5	72	9,5	77	10,2	48	6,4	170	22,5	537	71,1
Total triglycerides	117	15,5	72	9,5	77	10,2	48	6,4	170	22,5	537	71,1
Triglycerides in VLDL	117	15,5	72	9,5	77	10,2	48	6,4	170	22,5	537	71,1
Triglycerides in LDL	117	15,5	72	9,5	77	10,2	48	6,4	170	22,5	537	71,1
Triglycerides in HDL	117	15,5	72	9,5	77	10,2	48	6,4	170	22,5	537	71,1
Total phosphoglycerides	117	15,5	72	9,5	78	10,3	48	6,4	171	22,7	536	71,0
Phosphatidylcholine and other cholin	117	15,5	72	9,5	78	10,3	48	6,4	171	22,7	536	71,0
Total cholines	117	15,5	72	9,5	78	10,3	48	6,4	171	22,7	536	71,0
Sphingomyelin	117	15,5	72	9,5	78	10,3	48	6,4	171	22,7	536	71,0
Apolipoprotein A-I	117	15,5	72	9,5	77	10,2	48	6,4	170	22,5	537	71,1
Apolipoprotein B	117	15,5	72	9,5	77	10,2	48	6,4	170	22,5	537	71,1
ApoBApoA	117	15,5	72	9,5	77	10,2	48	6,4	170	22,5	537	71,1
Docosahexaenoic acid	117	15,5	72	9,5	78	10,3	48	6,4	171	22,7	536	71,0
Linoleic acid	117	15,5	72	9,5	78	10,3	48	6,4	171	22,7	536	71,0
Omega-3 fatty acids	117	15,5	72	9,5	78	10,3	48	6,4	171	22,7	536	71,0
Omega-6 fatty acids	117	15,5	72	9,5	78	10,3	48	6,4	171	22,7	536	71,0
Polyunsaturated fatty acids	117	15,5	72	9,5	78	10,3	48	6,4	171	22,7	536	71,0
Monounsaturated fatty acids	117	15,5	72	9,5	78	10,3	48	6,4	171	22,7	536	71,0
Saturated fatty acids	117	15,5	72	9,5	78	10,3	48	6,4	171	22,7	536	71,0
Docosahexaenoic to total fatty acids	117	15,5	72	9,5	79	10,5	48	6,4	172	22,8	535	70,9

Linoleic to total fatty acids	117	15,5	72	9,5	79	10,5	48	6,4	172	22,8	535	70,9
Omega-3 to total fatty acids	117	15,5	72	9,5	79	10,5	48	6,4	172	22,8	535	70,9
Omega-6 to total fatty acids	117	15,5	74	9,8	79	10,5	49	6,5	172	22,8	534	70,7
Polyunsaturated to total fatty acids	117	15,5	72	9,5	79	10,5	48	6,4	172	22,8	535	70,9
Monounsaturated to total fatty acids	117	15,5	72	9,5	78	10,3	48	6,4	171	22,7	536	71,0
Saturated to total fatty acids	117	15,5	72	9,5	78	10,3	48	6,4	171	22,7	536	71,0
Glucose	118	15,6	73	9,7	78	10,3	49	6,5	171	22,7	535	70,9
Lactate	118	15,6	74	9,8	80	10,6	49	6,5	174	23,1	532	70,5
Citrate	118	15,6	75	9,9	79	10,5	50	6,6	172	22,8	533	70,6
Alanine	117	15,5	72	9,5	77	10,2	48	6,4	170	22,5	537	71,1
Glutamine	119	15,8	72	9,5	78	10,3	48	6,4	173	22,9	534	70,7
Histidine	117	15,5	72	9,5	77	10,2	48	6,4	170	22,5	537	71,1
Isoleucine	117	15,5	72	9,5	78	10,3	48	6,4	171	22,7	536	71,0
Leucine	117	15,5	72	9,5	78	10,3	48	6,4	171	22,7	536	71,0
Valine	117	15,5	72	9,5	78	10,3	48	6,4	171	22,7	536	71,0
Phenylalanine	117	15,5	73	9,7	77	10,2	48	6,4	171	22,7	536	71,0
Tyrosine	117	15,5	72	9,5	78	10,3	48	6,4	171	22,7	536	71,0
Acetate	117	15,5	72	9,5	77	10,2	48	6,4	170	22,5	537	71,1
Acetoacetate	119	15,8	73	9,7	81	10,7	48	6,4	176	23,3	531	70,3
3-hydroxybutyrate	120	15,9	79	10,5	79	10,5	49	6,5	180	23,8	526	69,7
Creatinine	117	15,5	72	9,5	78	10,3	48	6,4	171	22,7	536	71,0
Albumin	117	15,5	72	9,5	77	10,2	48	6,4	170	22,5	537	71,1
Glycoprotein acetyls	117	15,5	72	9,5	77	10,2	48	6,4	170	22,5	537	71,1

Supplementary Table 2. Numeric values of mean differences and 99.8% CIs in the metabolic measures during pregnancy in which nonobese women with GDM (NOGDM), obese women with GDM (OGDM), and obese women with no GDM (O) differed similarly from the controls (Panel A); in which differences of obese women with GDM (OGDM) from controls were more pronounced than were the differences of NOGDM or O from controls (Panel B); and in which differences of OGDM or O from controls were more pronounced than differences of NOGDM from controls (Panel C). Numeric values seen in the left panels represent differences in the combined PREDO-RADIEL cohort, and in the right panels in the independent ITU replication cohort. Associations adjusted for cohort (PREDO-RADIEL), gestational week at blood sampling, maternal age, parity, education, and smoking and alcohol use during pregnancy.

Metabolic measure	Group	PREDO-RADIEL				ITU				Mean difference from controls in the same direction
		MD (SD units)	Lower CI	Upper CI	P value	MD (SD units)	Lower CI	Upper CI	P value	
Panel A										
Lipoprotein subclasses										
Very large VLDL	Nonobese GDM	0,3628	0,1252	0,6005	0,0000	0,4052	0,1676	0,6428	0,0009	YES
	Obese GDM	0,4387	0,1896	0,6878	0,0000	0,5656	0,1271	1,0041	0,0116	YES
	Obese non-GDM	0,3404	0,1508	0,5300	0,0000	0,3555	-0,2120	0,9230	0,2189	YES
Large VLDL	Nonobese GDM	0,4432	0,1646	0,7218	0,0000	0,3753	0,1396	0,6110	0,0019	YES
	Obese GDM	0,6162	0,3257	0,9066	0,0000	0,4956	0,0605	0,9306	0,0257	YES
	Obese non-GDM	0,4609	0,2375	0,6843	0,0000	0,2800	-0,2830	0,8429	0,3289	YES
Medium VLDL	Nonobese GDM	0,3211	0,0518	0,5904	0,0002	0,2614	0,0420	0,4808	0,0197	YES
	Obese GDM	0,3246	0,0438	0,6054	0,0004	0,1502	-0,2546	0,5550	0,4664	YES
	Obese non-GDM	0,2735	0,0578	0,4892	0,0001	-0,0430	-0,5668	0,4807	0,8718	
Small VLDL	Nonobese GDM	0,3688	0,1153	0,6223	0,0000	0,2739	0,0550	0,4928	0,0143	YES
	Obese GDM	0,4648	0,2007	0,7290	0,0000	0,2451	-0,1588	0,6490	0,2336	YES
	Obese non-GDM	0,3388	0,1354	0,5421	0,0000	-0,0066	-0,5292	0,5159	0,9802	
Very small VLDL	Nonobese GDM	0,2646	0,0209	0,5083	0,0008	0,2615	0,0372	0,4857	0,0224	YES
	Obese GDM	0,3031	0,0492	0,5570	0,0002	0,0152	-0,3985	0,4289	0,9425	YES
	Obese non-GDM	0,2568	0,0612	0,4525	0,0001	-0,0551	-0,5904	0,4802	0,8397	
Medium LDL (a)	Nonobese GDM	0,2630	-0,0264	0,5524	0,0050	0,2583	0,0182	0,4983	0,0350	YES
	Obese GDM	0,3319	0,0307	0,6332	0,0007	0,1277	-0,3153	0,5708	0,5714	YES
	Obese non-GDM	0,3107	0,0786	0,5429	0,0000	-0,0252	-0,5985	0,5482	0,9313	
Small LDL (a)	Nonobese GDM	0,2707	-0,0076	0,5490	0,0026	0,2586	0,0203	0,4970	0,0335	YES
	Obese GDM	0,3370	0,0474	0,6266	0,0003	0,0214	-0,4185	0,4613	0,9237	YES
	Obese non-GDM	0,2949	0,0715	0,5183	0,0000	-0,0758	-0,6451	0,4935	0,7937	

Lipoprotein particle size										
Mean diameter of VLDL particles	Nonobese GDM	0,4354	0,1191	0,7518	0,0000	0,3244	0,0837	0,5652	0,0084	YES
	Obese GDM	0,7355	0,4056	1,0654	0,0000	0,6363	0,1919	1,0806	0,0051	YES
	Obese non-GDM	0,4985	0,2448	0,7523	0,0000	0,4262	-0,1489	1,0012	0,1460	YES
Cholesterol										
Total cholesterol in VLDL	Nonobese GDM	0,3172	0,0556	0,5788	0,0002	0,2862	0,0644	0,5080	0,0115	YES
	Obese GDM	0,3836	0,1108	0,6563	0,0000	0,2042	-0,2049	0,6134	0,3272	YES
	Obese non-GDM	0,3105	0,1008	0,5201	0,0000	0,0070	-0,5224	0,5364	0,9794	YES
Remnant cholesterol (a)	Nonobese GDM	0,2496	-0,0173	0,5165	0,0038	0,2371	0,0114	0,4629	0,0396	YES
	Obese GDM	0,2232	-0,0548	0,5012	0,0130	-0,1078	-0,5243	0,3088	0,6114	
	Obese non-GDM	0,2309	0,0168	0,4449	0,0009	-0,1078	-0,6468	0,4311	0,6943	
Glycerides and phospholipids										
Triglycerides in VLDL	Nonobese GDM	0,4535	0,1845	0,7225	0,0000	0,3782	0,1420	0,6144	0,0018	YES
	Obese GDM	0,6532	0,3726	0,9338	0,0000	0,5298	0,0940	0,9657	0,0173	YES
	Obese non-GDM	0,4703	0,2546	0,6860	0,0000	0,3872	-0,1769	0,9512	0,1780	YES
Triglycerides in LDL	Nonobese GDM	0,2755	0,0442	0,5068	0,0002	0,2651	0,0437	0,4865	0,0190	YES
	Obese GDM	0,3924	0,1515	0,6333	0,0000	0,0540	-0,3545	0,4624	0,7952	YES
	Obese non-GDM	0,2657	0,0799	0,4516	0,0000	0,0151	-0,5133	0,5436	0,9551	YES
Triglycerides in HDL	Nonobese GDM	0,3017	0,0622	0,5412	0,0001	0,3230	0,0938	0,5522	0,0059	YES
	Obese GDM	0,3533	0,1032	0,6034	0,0000	0,2672	-0,1558	0,6901	0,2151	YES
	Obese non-GDM	0,2422	0,0503	0,4341	0,0001	0,2529	-0,2943	0,8001	0,3642	YES
Apolipoproteins										
Apolipoprotein B (a)	Nonobese GDM	0,2675	-0,0072	0,5422	0,0026	0,2344	-0,0046	0,4735	0,0546	YES
	Obese GDM	0,3113	0,0255	0,5971	0,0008	-0,0611	-0,5023	0,3801	0,7856	
	Obese non-GDM	0,2848	0,0642	0,5054	0,0001	-0,1688	-0,7397	0,4021	0,5614	
Ratio of apolipoprotein B to apolipoprotein A-I	Nonobese GDM	0,3016	0,0203	0,5830	0,0009	0,1367	-0,0957	0,3692	0,2483	YES
	Obese GDM	0,4386	0,1458	0,7315	0,0000	0,0606	-0,3684	0,4896	0,7815	YES
	Obese non-GDM	0,3573	0,1312	0,5834	0,0000	-0,2488	-0,8039	0,3063	0,3789	
Fatty acids										
Monounsaturated fatty acids	Nonobese GDM	0,4022	0,1556	0,6489	0,0000	0,2996	0,0860	0,5133	0,0061	YES
	Obese GDM	0,6225	0,3653	0,8796	0,0000	0,3142	-0,0800	0,7083	0,1179	YES
	Obese non-GDM	0,4655	0,2678	0,6632	0,0000	0,2938	-0,2162	0,8037	0,2582	YES
Saturated fatty acids	Nonobese GDM	0,3250	0,0769	0,5731	0,0001	0,3429	0,1192	0,5667	0,0027	YES
	Obese GDM	0,5137	0,2554	0,7720	0,0000	0,0811	-0,3317	0,4939	0,6996	YES
	Obese non-GDM	0,3795	0,1803	0,5786	0,0000	0,2402	-0,2939	0,7743	0,3772	YES

Panel B										
Fatty acids ratios										
Linoleic to total fatty acids	Nonobese GDM	-0,3343	-0,6649	-0,0036	0,0018	-0,2102	-0,4535	0,0331	0,0902	YES
	Obese GDM	-1,0719	-1,4163	-0,7275	0,0000	-0,4141	-0,8630	0,0349	0,0706	YES
	Obese non-GDM	-0,7146	-0,9819	-0,4473	0,0000	-0,3974	-0,9783	0,1836	0,1796	YES
Polyunsaturated to total fatty acids	Nonobese GDM	-0,3494	-0,5974	-0,1013	0,0000	-0,2969	-0,5293	-0,0646	0,0124	YES
	Obese GDM	-0,8645	-1,1227	-0,6063	0,0000	-0,4792	-0,9080	-0,0503	0,0286	YES
	Obese non-GDM	-0,6027	-0,8024	-0,4031	0,0000	-0,5167	-1,0717	0,0383	0,0680	YES
Glycolysis related metabolites										
Glucose	Nonobese GDM	0,5045	0,2402	0,7688	0,0000	0,4126	0,1861	0,6391	0,0004	YES
	Obese GDM	0,9879	0,7129	1,2630	0,0000	0,4162	-0,0019	0,8343	0,0510	YES
	Obese non-GDM	0,1572	-0,0565	0,3709	0,0219	-0,1510	-0,6920	0,3900	0,5837	
Citrate	Nonobese GDM	0,3298	0,0416	0,6180	0,0004	0,2604	0,0134	0,5073	0,0388	YES
	Obese GDM	0,8421	0,5413	1,1429	0,0000	0,0119	-0,4438	0,4676	0,9591	YES
	Obese non-GDM	0,4477	0,2162	0,6792	0,0000	0,0527	-0,5370	0,6424	0,8607	YES
Branched-chain amino acids										
Valine	Nonobese GDM	0,2128	-0,1212	0,5467	0,0482	0,1133	-0,1395	0,3662	0,3788	YES
	Obese GDM	0,7977	0,4503	1,1452	0,0000	0,1437	-0,3229	0,6103	0,5452	YES
	Obese non-GDM	0,4237	0,1541	0,6932	0,0000	-0,2885	-0,8923	0,3153	0,3483	
Ketone bodies										
3-hydroxybutyrate	Nonobese GDM	0,2069	-0,0555	0,4692	0,0147	0,2240	-0,0135	0,4614	0,0645	YES
	Obese GDM	0,6440	0,3696	0,9183	0,0000	-0,0372	-0,4754	0,4010	0,8677	
	Obese non-GDM	0,3401	0,1304	0,5497	0,0000	0,0759	-0,4911	0,6430	0,7925	YES
Amino acids										
Alanine (a)	Nonobese GDM	0,1770	-0,1160	0,4699	0,0614	-0,0775	-0,3281	0,1732	0,5439	
	Obese GDM	0,2385	-0,0676	0,5446	0,0159	-0,1948	-0,6574	0,2677	0,4083	
	Obese non-GDM	0,0554	-0,1798	0,2906	0,4654	-0,4036	-1,0022	0,1950	0,1858	

Panel C										
Lipoprotein subclasses										
Extremely large VLDL	Nonobese GDM	0,4240	0,1967	0,6513	0,0000	0,3521	0,1085	0,5957	0,0047	YES
	Obese GDM	0,6655	0,4270	0,9041	0,0000	0,6479	0,1983	1,0974	0,0048	YES
	Obese non-GDM	0,4904	0,3083	0,6724	0,0000	0,4997	-0,0820	1,0815	0,0921	YES
Very large HDL	Nonobese GDM	-0,0854	-0,3800	0,2092	0,3691	0,0560	-0,1765	0,2885	0,6363	
	Obese GDM	-0,5391	-0,8463	-0,2320	0,0000	-0,6264	-1,0555	-0,1972	0,0043	YES
	Obese non-GDM	-0,3445	-0,5805	-0,1084	0,0000	-0,1424	-0,6977	0,4129	0,6146	YES
Large HDL	Nonobese GDM	-0,1568	-0,4178	0,1041	0,0630	0,0463	-0,1892	0,2818	0,6994	
	Obese GDM	-0,6161	-0,8891	-0,3430	0,0000	-0,5130	-0,9476	-0,0783	0,0208	YES
	Obese non-GDM	-0,3628	-0,5724	-0,1532	0,0000	-0,0453	-0,6078	0,5171	0,8743	YES
Small HDL (a)	Nonobese GDM	0,1436	-0,1809	0,4682	0,1703	0,1661	-0,0853	0,4176	0,1949	
	Obese GDM	0,4680	0,1299	0,8060	0,0000	0,2966	-0,1675	0,7607	0,2098	YES
	Obese non-GDM	0,4301	0,1693	0,6908	0,0000	0,1796	-0,4209	0,7801	0,5570	YES
Lipoprotein particle size										
Mean diameter of HDL particles	Nonobese GDM	-0,1809	-0,4609	0,0990	0,0456	-0,0385	-0,2774	0,2004	0,7516	YES
	Obese GDM	-0,6548	-0,9469	-0,3628	0,0000	-0,6031	-1,0441	-0,1622	0,0074	YES
	Obese non-GDM	-0,4498	-0,6745	-0,2251	0,0000	-0,1149	-0,6856	0,4557	0,6924	YES
Cholesterol										
Total cholesterol in HDL	Nonobese GDM	-0,1901	-0,4719	0,0916	0,0368	0,0368	-0,2023	0,2758	0,7626	
	Obese GDM	-0,5649	-0,8589	-0,2709	0,0000	-0,4639	-0,9051	-0,0227	0,0394	YES
	Obese non-GDM	-0,3047	-0,5312	-0,0783	0,0000	-0,0101	-0,5810	0,5608	0,9723	YES
Glycerides and phospholipids										
Total triglycerides	Nonobese GDM	0,4184	0,1522	0,6847	0,0000	0,3758	0,1405	0,6111	0,0018	YES
	Obese GDM	0,7633	0,4863	1,0403	0,0000	0,4527	0,0185	0,8869	0,0410	YES
	Obese non-GDM	0,5129	0,2981	0,7277	0,0000	0,3430	-0,2188	0,9049	0,2309	YES
Fatty acids ratios										
Docosahexaenoic to total fatty acids (a)	Nonobese GDM	-0,1891	-0,4873	0,1091	0,0496	-0,0533	-0,2911	0,1846	0,6601	YES
	Obese GDM	-0,4484	-0,7589	-0,1379	0,0000	-0,3339	-0,7729	0,1051	0,1356	YES
	Obese non-GDM	-0,3868	-0,6265	-0,1472	0,0000	-0,4186	-0,9866	0,1494	0,1483	YES
Omega-6 to total fatty acids	Nonobese GDM	-0,3888	-0,6361	-0,1414	0,0000	-0,3439	-0,5823	-0,1054	0,0048	YES
	Obese GDM	-0,8041	-1,0623	-0,5459	0,0000	-0,4077	-0,8478	0,0324	0,0693	YES
	Obese non-GDM	-0,5530	-0,7518	-0,3543	0,0000	-0,3734	-0,9430	0,1961	0,1982	YES

Monounsaturated to total fatty acids	Nonobese GDM	0,4295	0,1529	0,7060	0,0000	0,1939	-0,0232	0,4109	0,0799	YES
	Obese GDM	0,8915	0,6030	1,1799	0,0000	0,6648	0,2643	1,0652	0,0012	YES
	Obese non-GDM	0,6352	0,4135	0,8568	0,0000	0,4328	-0,0853	0,9509	0,1014	YES
Amino acids										
Glutamine	Nonobese GDM	-0,1405	-0,4427	0,1616	0,1496	-0,1398	-0,3889	0,1092	0,2705	YES
	Obese GDM	-0,4958	-0,8107	-0,1808	0,0000	-0,5210	-0,9805	-0,0616	0,0263	YES
	Obese non-GDM	-0,3544	-0,5970	-0,1118	0,0000	-1,0304	-1,6248	-0,4359	0,0007	YES
Branched-chain amino acids										
Isoleucine	Nonobese GDM	0,2731	-0,0639	0,6101	0,0121	-0,0230	-0,2776	0,2317	0,8594	
	Obese GDM	0,7502	0,3995	1,1009	0,0000	0,0692	-0,4007	0,5392	0,7723	YES
	Obese non-GDM	0,4739	0,2018	0,7460	0,0000	-0,2518	-0,8600	0,3564	0,4163	
Leucine	Nonobese GDM	0,0848	-0,2419	0,4115	0,4170	-0,0318	-0,2848	0,2213	0,8053	
	Obese GDM	0,5521	0,2121	0,8922	0,0000	0,0630	-0,4040	0,5301	0,7910	YES
	Obese non-GDM	0,4058	0,1419	0,6696	0,0000	-0,3267	-0,9311	0,2777	0,2886	
Aromatic amino acids										
Phenylalanine	Nonobese GDM	-0,2027	-0,4969	0,0914	0,0328	-0,1638	-0,4185	0,0909	0,2069	YES
	Obese GDM	0,3904	0,0832	0,6975	0,0001	-0,0520	-0,5221	0,4181	0,8280	
	Obese non-GDM	0,3314	0,0948	0,5681	0,0000	-0,2878	-0,8961	0,3205	0,3530	
Tyrosine	Nonobese GDM	-0,0148	-0,2998	0,2701	0,8719	-0,0292	-0,2828	0,2244	0,8212	YES
	Obese GDM	0,5108	0,2130	0,8086	0,0000	-0,1052	-0,5733	0,3629	0,6590	
	Obese non-GDM	0,3017	0,0728	0,5307	0,0000	-0,0987	-0,7044	0,5071	0,7491	
Ketone bodies										
Acetoacetate	Nonobese GDM	0,2297	-0,0418	0,5013	0,0089	0,1079	-0,1399	0,3558	0,3925	YES
	Obese GDM	0,6320	0,3479	0,9160	0,0000	0,0292	-0,4339	0,4923	0,9014	YES
	Obese non-GDM	0,4418	0,2245	0,6592	0,0000	-0,2461	-0,8291	0,3369	0,4072	
Fluid balance										
Albumin	Nonobese GDM	-0,0101	-0,2250	0,2048	0,8838	-0,0128	-0,2533	0,2277	0,9169	YES
	Obese GDM	-0,3205	-0,5447	-0,0963	0,0000	-0,0582	-0,5020	0,3857	0,7969	YES
	Obese non-GDM	-0,3241	-0,4969	-0,1513	0,0000	-0,2458	-0,8202	0,3286	0,4008	YES
Inflammation										
Glycoprotein acetyls	Nonobese GDM	0,3551	0,0724	0,6379	0,0001	0,3500	0,1231	0,5769	0,0026	YES
	Obese GDM	0,9826	0,6880	1,2771	0,0000	0,5389	0,1203	0,9575	0,0117	YES
	Obese non-GDM	0,8013	0,5744	1,0281	0,0000	0,5781	0,0365	1,1197	0,0365	YES

(a) Metabolic measures significant in PREDO-RADIEL only at the first measurement point, but for the sake of clarity, mean difference across pregnancy is reported in the table. Directions in the associations between the group and the measure do not, however, differ between the first measurement point and mean across pregnancy.